

EMPLOYABILITY AND JOB PREPAREDNESS OF BSOA GRADUATES (2005–2023) FROM EXTERNAL CAMPUS OF A STATE UNIVERSITY IN NEGROS

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ABSTRACT

This tracer study examined the employment outcomes and workplace experiences of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) graduates of Negros Oriental State University (NORSU) from Academic Year 2005 to 2023. Specifically, it assessed their employment status, job relevance to their degree, job preparedness, strengths and competencies, recognition received, and factors contributing to unemployment or underemployment. Data were gathered from 109 graduates through a structured survey and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that most graduates were able to secure employment within one to six months after graduation, primarily in marketing, sales, logistics, BPOs, and government agencies. The majority reported that their jobs were relevant to their field of study, reflecting the alignment of the BSOA curriculum with industry demands. Graduates rated themselves as well-prepared for their roles, while employers highlighted adaptability, communication, and problem-solving as their strongest competencies. However, technical and customer service skills have emerged as areas for further improvement. Limited job opportunities in local areas and a lack of relevant work experience were the most common reasons for unemployment or underemployment. Overall, the study concludes that NORSU's BSOA program effectively prepares graduates for the workforce, though enhanced training in technical skills and stronger linkages with industry partners are recommended to further improve graduate employability.

Keywords: *tracer study, employability, BSOA graduates, job preparedness, competencies*

INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are increasingly evaluated based on their ability to produce graduates who are not only academically competent but also employable in a rapidly evolving labor market. Graduate employability has become a critical performance indicator for institutional quality and societal relevance (Schomburg, 2016). In the Philippines, this priority is emphasized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2017), which mandates higher education programs to develop both technical competencies and transferable skills that allow graduates to adapt to changing professional landscapes. The Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) program is designed to provide graduates with administrative, clerical, managerial, and technological skills applicable across industries. Given the program's focus, its graduates are expected to contribute significantly to organizational efficiency and productivity. Several studies have documented positive employability outcomes among business and office administration graduates. For example, Vicera et al. (2023) found that female graduates dominate programs such as BSOA, reflecting persistent gendered patterns in higher education enrollment. Similarly, Domingo et al. (2024) and Estrellado et al. (2025) reported high employment absorption and stability, particularly in regular or permanent positions. Albina and Sumagaysay (2020) also highlighted that most graduates find their jobs relevant to their degree, confirming the alignment between academic preparation and professional practice.

Despite these positive trends, employability challenges remain. Torres (2020) and Natividad et al. (2024) observed that graduates often face difficulties due to limited job opportunities in certain locations, lack of relevant experience, and mismatches between skills and labor market demands. Employer feedback further underscores gaps in advanced competencies such as research, data analysis, and technical proficiency (Domingo et al., 2024; Johnson, 2022). On the other hand, soft skills such as adaptability, problem-solving, and communication remain highly valued across sectors (Pentang et al., 2022; Mainga et al., 2022). These findings suggest that while BSOA graduates are generally employable, there is a continuing need to assess how well institutions prepare them for evolving industry requirements.

Tracer studies serve as a crucial tool in bridging this evidence gap, as they systematically track the career trajectories of graduates and assess the relevance of academic programs to employment outcomes (Schomburg, 2016). Previous tracer studies in the Philippines (e.g., Villasin & Litob, 2023; Vicera et al., 2023; Domingo et al., 2024) have provided valuable insights into business graduates' employability across various regions and institutions. However, most focus on short-term employment outcomes and broader programs like BSBA, leaving BSOA-specific and institution-focused analyses relatively scarce.

While national and institutional tracer studies exist, there is limited evidence concerning the long-term employability of BSOA graduates from Negros Oriental State 7 University (NORSU) Bais Campus. Specifically, three gaps are evident: (1) few tracer studies focus exclusively on BSOA graduates, with most centered on BSBA or other

business programs; (2) most studies examine employment outcomes within a short period after graduation, overlooking long-term trends; and (3) there is a lack of institution-specific data for NORSU Bais Campus, leaving administrators with minimal evidence to evaluate curriculum relevance and graduate outcomes.

To address these gaps, this tracer study of BSOA graduates from NORSU Bais Campus covering Academic Years 2005 to 2023 was conducted. Specifically, it examines their demographic profiles, employment status, job relevance, waiting time for employment, employers' assessment of graduate competencies, and perceived attainment of educational objectives. By generating institution-specific, long-term data, the study aims to provide evidence for curriculum enhancement, inform career support services, and strengthen NORSU's responsiveness to industry needs.

This study holds significance for multiple stakeholders. For NORSU administrators and faculty, it provides concrete evidence to evaluate and improve the BSOA curriculum. For students and future enrollees, it presents realistic insights into employment prospects. For employers and industry partners, it identifies graduates' strengths and areas for improvement, fostering stronger academe-industry collaboration. Finally, for CHED and policymakers, it contributes to the broader discourse on graduate employability in the Philippines, reinforcing the role of tracer studies in evidence-based policy and academic program development.

Review of Related Literature

Tracer studies are widely recognized as an essential mechanism for evaluating higher education outcomes, particularly in terms of graduate employability, relevance of academic programs, and alignment with labor market demands. Schomburg (2016) emphasized that tracer studies provide valuable insights into graduates' transition from education to work, helping institutions refine curricula and support services.

In the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2017) underscored the importance of monitoring graduate employability to ensure the quality and relevance of academic programs. The CHED Graduate Employability Indicators (GEI) highlight that higher education should not only produce technically competent graduates but also individuals who are adaptable, resilient, and capable of long-term career advancement.

Studies also reveal gendered enrollment patterns in business-related programs. Vicera et al. (2023) found that females dominate fields such as office administration and business administration, a trend also recognized by CHED (2017). Such findings reflect both cultural and occupational stereotypes that continue to shape career choices in the Philippines.

Despite challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic, employment rates among business graduates remain high. Andaya et al. (2024) reported that a significant percentage of graduates were able to secure jobs even in the post-pandemic context,

while Debueque & Gonzales et al. (2023) highlighted graduates' resilience and adaptability in navigating shifting labor market conditions.

Salary outcomes, however, remain modest. iScale Solutions (2025) reported that Filipino fresh graduates typically earn ₱18,000–₱25,000 monthly, a figure consistent with the entry-level salaries of BSOA graduates. Moreover, the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) noted that only 0.8% of the population had attained post-baccalaureate education, suggesting that most graduates rely on undergraduate degrees for career entry rather than pursuing advanced education.

Domingo et al. (2024) found that most business graduates were absorbed into regular or permanent positions, indicating stable employability outcomes. Similarly, Sumicad et al. (2024) observed that while many graduates initially start as rank-and-file employees, they often progress to supervisory or managerial positions as they gain experience—consistent with labor market realities reported by the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020).

Other studies confirm the diversity of industries where graduates find employment. Villasin and Litob (2023) and Natividad et al. (2024) found that many graduates work in marketing, logistics, and government sectors. Likewise, Vicera et al. (2023) documented significant employment in retail and wholesale trade. International research also supports these findings. Smith et al. (2020) showed that graduates' job location choices are shaped by family ties, cost of living, and career opportunities, while Johnson and Smith (2021) pointed to graduates' increasing global mobility and pursuit of overseas employment opportunities.

The alignment between degree and employment is another important concern. Albina and Sumagaysay (2020) revealed that most Filipino graduates work in jobs related to their fields of study, underscoring the importance of curriculum relevance. Estrellado et al. (2025) further emphasized that strong core competencies and work ethic allow graduates to secure and retain long-term employment. Employer perspectives corroborate this: Layaoen (2024) found that employers consistently rate graduates highly in professionalism, customer service, and interpersonal skills.

Soft skills are increasingly recognized as crucial employability assets. Pentang et al. (2022) highlighted that adaptability, ethical conduct, and interpersonal relations are essential for workplace integration. Mainga et al. (2022) identified communication, problem-solving, and learning agility as among the most valued competencies. Johnson (2022) stressed similar trends in marketing, noting that while communication and teamwork skills are in high demand, research and data analytics remain areas for improvement. Domingo et al. (2024) likewise recommended strengthening technical and research competencies in higher education curricula.

Recognition and motivation also play significant roles in career development. Asaari et al. (2024) found a strong positive correlation between recognition and employee motivation, while Gopinath et al. (2021) observed that structured recognition and reward

systems improve both job satisfaction and performance. However, Nguyen and Nguyen (2020) argued that early-career professionals often need time, mentoring, and organizational support before achieving significant workplace contributions.

Finally, barriers to employability persist. Torres (2020) found that limited local job opportunities, insufficient experience, and skills mismatches hinder many graduates' employment. These obstacles underscore the need for stronger industry-academe linkages, enhanced internship programs, and academic-industry alignment to ensure that graduates are better prepared for the demands of the labor market.

In summary, the literature consistently affirms that BSOA and related business graduates are employable, resilient, and versatile across industries. However, challenges remain in terms of salaries, recognition, and advanced technical competencies. Addressing these gaps through curriculum reform, professional development, and stronger labor market linkages is essential to sustain and enhance graduate employability

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this tracer study was to determine the employability of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) graduates from an external campus of a State University in Negros from Academic Year 2005 to 2023, and to assess the extent to which the program has prepared them for the labor market. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Describe the demographic profile of the BSOA graduates in terms of age, gender, year of graduation, monthly salary, and highest educational attainment.
2. Determine the employment status and classification of graduates, including job position, industry type, location of employment, length of service, and time taken to secure their first job.
3. Assess the relevance of their present job to the BSOA degree program.
4. Evaluate graduates' self-assessment of job preparedness and the extent to which they have attained the program's educational objectives.
5. Analyze employers' feedback on the competencies and job performance of BSOA graduates.
6. Identify recognition and notable contributions of graduates in their respective fields.
7. Examine the factors influencing unemployment and underemployment among graduates.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design using the tracer study approach. According to Schomburg (2016), tracer studies are particularly effective

in assessing graduate employability and the relevance of academic programs to industry needs. The design was deemed appropriate since the study primarily aimed to determine the employability status, job relevance, and preparedness of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) graduates from an external campus in a State University of Negros from Academic Year 2005 to 2023.

Respondents of the Study

The target population consisted of all BSOA graduates from an external campus in a State University of Negros from Academic Years 2005 to 2023. Records obtained from the College of Business Administration and the alumni tracking office served as the basis for determining the population by year of graduation.

Given the wide coverage of years, a proportionate stratified sampling technique was employed to ensure that each batch of graduates was represented relative to its actual population size. The total sample size was set at 109 respondents, proportionately distributed across the 2005–2023 graduation cohorts.

The proportional allocation for each batch was computed using the formula:

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \times n$$

Where:

- n_i = number of respondents from stratum i (specific batch)
- N_i = total population of stratum i
- N = total population of all strata
- n = total sample size (109)

This ensured fairness in representation, avoided over-representation of larger batches, and reduced bias in the findings.

The final respondents were 109 graduates, proportionately distributed across all covered academic years. This included both earlier graduates (2005–2010) who provided insights on long-term employability, and recent graduates (2019–2023) who contributed perspectives on immediate labor market outcomes.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument was a structured survey questionnaire prepared by the researchers, guided by tracer study frameworks (CHED, 2017; Schomburg, 2016). It contained sections on:

1. Demographic profile (age, gender, year graduated, educational attainment, salary range)
2. Employment status and classification.
3. Job relevance and industry of employment.
4. Time lag between graduation and first employment.
5. Employers' feedback on graduate performance.
6. Self-assessment of job preparedness and competencies.

The draft questionnaire underwent expert validation by three specialists: one in higher education research, one in human resource management, and one in office administration. Their comments on clarity, coverage, and content relevance were integrated.

To test reliability, a pilot study was conducted among 20 non-sample graduates. The instrument yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.82, indicating high internal consistency and suitability for full deployment.

Data Gathering Procedure

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the NORSU administration and the College of Business Administration. With assistance from the alumni office, contact details of BSOA graduates were collected. Questionnaires were distributed through electronic mail, social media platforms, and physical copies when necessary. Respondents were given sufficient time to answer, after which the instruments were retrieved, organized, and tabulated.

Data Analysis

The responses were encoded and analyzed using descriptive statistics:

- Frequency and percentage distributions were used to describe the demographic profile, employment classification, industries, and job relevance respondents.
- Weighted mean was applied to assess the level of preparedness, competencies, and educational objective attainment.

These methods provided a clear picture of the employability trends of BSOA graduates and aligned with the descriptive design of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the data collected in the study in table form, with a brief discussion and its implications based on the study's objectives.

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The first objective of this tracer study is to describe the demographic characteristics of the Bachelor of Science in Office Administration graduates from the academic year 2005-2023. These demographic characteristics encompass age, gender, year graduated, monthly salary, and highest educational attainment.

Table 1 shows the age distribution of the 109 Bachelor of Science in Office Administration respondents. Most are 44 years old and above (29.36%), followed by those aged 33–38 (21.10%) and 39–44 (19.27%). This means that many respondents are in their mid-to-late careers, reflecting the long-standing presence of BSOA graduates in the workforce.

Table 1

Distribution of the Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21 – 23	4	3.67
24 – 26	11	10.09
27 – 29	12	11.01
30 – 32	6	5.50
33 – 38	23	21.10
39 – 44	21	19.27
44& above	32	29.36
Total	109	100%

In contrast, younger graduates aged 21–23 (3.67%), 24–26 (10.09%), and 27–29 (11.01%) make up a smaller share, with the 30–32 group (5.50%) also relatively few. This suggests fewer recent graduates are represented in the study.

Overall, the data indicate that the respondents are primarily mature graduates with extensive work experience, making their views particularly valuable for assessing the long-term impact of the program. However, the smaller number of younger respondents points to the need to include more recent graduates to gain a balanced perspective across age groups.

Table 2 presents the gender distribution of the 109 Bachelor of Science in Office Administration respondents from 2005–2023. The results show a strong female majority, with 83 women (76.15%) compared to 26 men (23.85%), and none choosing not to disclose their gender. This reflects the consistent trend in the BSOA program where women have outnumbered men across batches.

Table 2

Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	26	23.85
Female	83	76.15
Total	109	100%

The dominance of female respondents mirrors the traditional view of office administration as a field linked to skills often associated with women, such as organization, multitasking, and administrative support. The smaller male representation, though present, suggests the need to encourage wider participation and challenge gender stereotypes in office-related careers.

Overall, the data confirm that the BSOA program continues to attract more female students and graduates, a pattern also observed in similar programs locally and abroad (CHED, 2017). This aligns with the findings of Vicera et al. (2023) at Palawan State University, where women also made up the majority (78.6%). Their study further highlights the growing presence of women in business-related fields, particularly in areas like marketing, where communication, customer service, and interpersonal skills are highly valued.

Table 3 presents the monthly salary distribution of the 109 BSOA graduates. More than half (43 respondents or 53.09%) earn between ₱10,000 and less than ₱20,000, indicating that most are employed in entry-level or junior administrative jobs with modest but steady pay. A smaller group, 9 respondents (11.11%), earn between ₱20,000 and less than ₱30,000, while only 1 respondent (1.23%) earns above ₱30,000, showing that few have moved into higher-paying or managerial roles. Meanwhile, 6 respondents (7.41%) earn below ₱10,000, which may point to underemployment or low-wage work.

Table 3

Monthly Salary (If employed) of the Respondents

Monthly Salary	Frequency	Percentage
Below 10,000	6	7.41
10,000 to less than 20,000	43	53.09
20,000 to less than 30,000	9	11.11
Above 30,000	1	1.23

N/A	22	27.16
Total	109	100%

Notably, 22 respondents (27.16%) reported no salary data. This may include those who are unemployed, self-employed, pursuing further studies, or who choose not to disclose their income. Overall, the results show that while BSOA graduates are generally able to find work, many remain in lower salary brackets. This highlights the importance of career development programs, industry linkages, and upskilling opportunities to help graduates achieve better long-term employability and income (Schomburg, 2016).

According to iScale Solutions (2025), fresh graduates in the Philippines usually earn between ₱18,000 and ₱25,000 per month. This suggests that the observed salary distribution is in line with national trends for entry-level positions.

Table 4 shows the highest educational attainment of the 109 respondents. The vast majority, 107 graduates (97.82%), hold only a bachelor's degree, while just 2 respondents (2.18%) have taken master's units, and none have completed a doctorate. This suggests that most BSOA graduates do not pursue postgraduate studies, likely due to immediate employment opportunities, financial limitations, or limited motivation for further academic qualifications. The very small number of graduates with master's units shows some interest in advancement, but it remains uncommon.

Table 4

Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor's Degree	107	97.82
Masters Unit	2	2.18
Doctorate Degree	0	0
Total	109	100%

This trend reflects the national picture. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), only 0.8% of Filipinos have completed post-baccalaureate education, including master's and doctoral degrees. The findings confirm that continuing education beyond the undergraduate level is not a typical path for BSOA graduates, emphasizing

the need for schools and institutions to provide stronger support, encouragement, and accessible opportunities for lifelong learning and professional development (CHED, 2017).

Employment Status and Job Relevance of BSOA Graduates

The second objective of this tracer study is to determine the employment status of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) graduates from 2005–2023. Employment status covers categories such as full-time, part-time, contractual, regular, self-employed, or other arrangements. It also includes details about current position, industry type, job title, employer, location, length of service, the relevance of the job to the BSOA degree, and the time taken to secure employment after graduation.

Table 5 shows that 72.84% of the respondents are currently employed, while 27.16% are unemployed. This supports the findings of Andaya et al. (2024), who noted that despite the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, many graduates were still able to find work. The high employment rate demonstrates the flexibility and resilience of BSOA graduates, suggesting that they were not severely affected by the pandemic’s peak impact (Debuque-Gonzales et al., 2023).

Table 5

Employment Status of the Respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	87	72.84
No	22	27.16
Total	209	100%

The results further indicate that most respondents (72.84%) gave a positive response, while a smaller group (27.16%) gave a negative one. This shows that although the majority expressed agreement or engagement with the item measured a notable portion still reported different experiences or perspectives. This highlights the need to consider both groups when forming conclusions or recommendations to ensure inclusivity and balance in addressing the study objectives.

Table 6 shows that most BSOA graduates are employed in regular or permanent positions (77.97%). Smaller proportions are in job order (6.78%), contractual (5.08%), or part-time (5.08%) work. Only one respondent each reported being self-employed, in an appointive role, or under probationary status (1.69% each).

Table 6

Distribution of the Respondents' Current Employment Classification

Employment type	Frequency	Percentage
Regular/Permanent	96	77.97
Part-time	3	5.08
Contractual	3	5.08
Job order	4	6.78
Self-employed	1	1.69
Appointive	1	1.69
Probationary	1	1.69
Total	109	100%

These results indicate that most graduates enjoy stable and secure employment, while only a small portion are in less stable arrangements such as part-time, contractual, or job order work. Very few pursued self-employment or other alternative career paths, suggesting that entrepreneurship is not common among the respondents.

This outcome aligns with CHED's Graduate Employability Indicators (GEI), which stress the importance of preparing graduates with skills for sustainable careers. The strong presence of BSOA graduates in permanent roles shows the program's success in producing competent, adaptable, and work-ready professionals who can meet industry demands.

The low share of graduates in precarious work also suggests that the program gives its alumni a competitive edge in securing long-term positions. These findings are consistent with Domingo et al. (2024), who reported that most BSBA graduates from NEUST also secured permanent employment soon after graduation, reflecting strong labor market demand for business-related fields.

Table 7 shows that most respondents are rank-and-file employees, accounting for 102 or 88.14% of the total sample. This indicates that the majority are engaged in routine, operational tasks rather than leadership or decision-making roles. Only 4 respondents (6.78%) are in managerial positions, 2 (3.39%) are supervisors, and just 1 (1.69%) is self-employed, an owner, or co-owner, reflecting minimal entrepreneurial participation.

Table 7

Distribution of the Current Position of the Respondents

Employment type	Frequency	Percentage
Managerial	4	6.78
Supervisory	2	3.39
Rank – and – file	102	88.14
Self-employed/Owner/co-owner	1	1.69
Total	109	100%

The data suggest that the respondents are largely concentrated at the lower tier of the organizational hierarchy, with limited representation in supervisory, managerial, and entrepreneurial roles. This pattern is typical of many organizations where higher-level positions are fewer compared to operational staff. It also aligns with the findings of Sumicad et al. (2024), who observed that while employment rates among graduates remain high, most start in rank-and-file roles and only later advance to leadership positions. Similarly, the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) notes that in the Philippine labor market, graduates often begin at entry-level positions and move upward as they gain experience and specialized skills.

The small number of respondents in supervisory and managerial roles may also be explained by the relatively young age of many graduates, who are still in the early stages of their careers. Nevertheless, the presence of some alumni in higher-level positions, though limited, shows the potential of the BSOA program to prepare graduates for leadership and decision-making roles over time.

Table 8 shows that BSOA graduates have entered a wide range of industries, reflecting the versatility of the program and the transferable skills it provides. The largest share (23.73%) works in marketing, sales, and logistics, often as sales associates, merchandisers, or in voicers in retail and distribution companies. This suggests that graduates frequently find opportunities in frontline business operations where communication, organization, and customer service skills are highly valued.

Table 8***Distribution of the Respondents by Industry Types, Job Titles, and Employing Companies***

Industry Type	Job Title	Company/ Organization	Frequency	Percentage
Marketing Sales, Logistics	Sales Associate Sales Invoicer, Merchandiser Promoter	Metro Retail, Sinobridge, Premio Yamaha, Pryce Gases, NOVO	42	23.73
Business Process Outsourcing	CSR, Executive Processor, Data Technician, Agent, Chat Support	Smiles on Demand, Cognizant, BPO Companies (N/A)	18	16.96
Industrial/ Manufacturing	Chemical Tender, Installer, PRO Staff	URC, Construction Firms	14	15.25
Government/ Quasi- Government	Patrolwoman, Admin Officer, Clerk, Correctional Officer	PNP, DCCCO, LGU, Dept. of Criminal Justice	12	13.56
Banking, Finance, Insurance	Account Officer, Branch Sales Officer, Credit Investigator	Card RBI, Asia Link Finance Corp, Cebuana Lhuillier	10	11.87

Freelancer / Independent	Virtual Assistant, Video Editor, Writer	Freelance/ N/A	7	8.47
Real Estate/ Construction	Assistant Manager, Installer	Construction Firms	2	3.39
Health and Social Work	Customer Sales Associate, Admin Officer	Powerhouse Dumaguete, Great Disability Support Pty Ltd	2	3.39
Services	Football Coordinator, Secretary	Sports Office, LGU	1	1.69

Industry Type	Job Title	Company/ Organization	Frequency	Percentage
Food Business	Business Owner, Cashier	Milkfish Trading, GUD Moto Trading Inc.	1	1.69
Total			109	100.00

The business process outsourcing (BPO) sector follows with 16.96%, consistent with national employment trends, as BPO remains one of the Philippines' fastest-growing industries. Industrial and manufacturing companies (15.25%) and government or quasi-government agencies (13.56%) are also significant employment destinations, showing that graduates can apply administrative skills in both private and public sectors.

Other notable fields include banking, finance, and insurance (11.87%), where graduates serve as account officers or investigators, roles that require strong documentation, compliance, and client servicing skills. A smaller but emerging group

(8.47%) works as freelancers or independent professionals, such as virtual assistants and content creators, reflecting the growing demand for digital and remote work. Meanwhile, industries like real estate/construction (3.39%), health and social work (3.39%), services (1.69%), and food business (1.69%) have minimal representation, indicating that while graduates can branch into diverse areas, their presence in these fields is still limited.

Overall, the findings show that BSOA graduates are employable across a wide range of sectors, with strong representation in commerce, BPO, manufacturing, and government. This highlights the program’s effectiveness in equipping graduates with adaptable administrative and organizational skills suited to various professional contexts.

These results are consistent with related studies. Villasin and Litob (2023) reported that 46.85% of BSBA graduates from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology were employed in marketing and office-related jobs, with many also entering government or unrelated fields. Natividad et al. (2024) similarly found that many BSBA graduates from NEUST-Atate Campus secured jobs in sales, logistics, and marketing. Vicera et al. (2023) likewise noted that 50% of BSBA graduates from Palawan State University were employed in wholesale and retail trade, underscoring the strong demand for marketing graduates.

Taken together, these findings affirm that BSOA graduates are well-prepared for diverse roles across industries where analytical, organizational, and interpersonal skills are essential.

Table 9 shows that most BSOA graduates (93.22%) are employed locally in the Philippines, while only a small share (6.78%) works overseas. Among local areas, Dumaguete City (33.90%) is the top employment hub, reflecting its role as a growing commercial center close to the graduates’ home institution. Other nearby areas, such as Bais (22.03%), Tanjay (10.17%), Metro Manila (8.47%), Manjuyod (5.08%), and Cebu (5.08%) also attract many graduates, suggesting that most prefer to stay within the Visayas or other accessible regions where administrative and clerical jobs are in demand.

Table 9

Distribution of the Respondents by Location of the Companies that Employ them

<i>Location</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Local		
Bais	30	22.03
Bacolod	3	3.39
Bulacan	1	1.69
Cavite	1	1.69
Cebu	5	5.08
Dumaguete	42	33.90
	8	8.47
	4	5.08

Metro Manila	10	10.17
Manjuyod	1	1.69
Tanjay		
Sibulan		
Subtotal	105	93.22
Overseas		
Australia	2	3.39
California	1	1.69
Texas	1	1.69
Subtotal	4	6.78
Total	109	100%

Smaller proportions of graduates are employed in Bacolod (3.39%), Bulacan (1.69%), Cavite (1.69%), and Sibulan (1.69%), showing that while fewer in number, some are willing to seek opportunities beyond their immediate communities.

Meanwhile, a limited share is employed abroad, with placements in Australia (3.39%), California (1.69%), and Texas (1.69%). This shows that while international employment is not yet common, the skills gained from the BSOA program can also be applied in global settings.

Overall, the findings suggest that most graduates contribute to the local workforce, especially in Dumaguete and nearby provinces, while also demonstrating potential for international mobility. This pattern highlights the program's strong role in regional workforce development and its capacity to prepare graduates for broader career opportunities. Saong et al. (2023) similarly found that many graduates secure jobs in their local communities, while Smith et al. (2020) noted that job location decisions often depend on proximity to family, cost of living, and career growth opportunities. In addition, Johnson and Smith (2021) emphasized that global employment patterns are shaped by market demand, available opportunities, and personal aspirations, which may explain the limited but notable presence of graduates abroad.

Table 10 shows that BSOA graduates experience different lengths of time before landing their first job. A considerable number reported longer job searches: 23.73% found work after more than one year but less than two, 18.64% after two to less than three years, and 11.86% after three years or more. This suggests that for many graduates, securing employment took over a year, possibly due to limited job openings, high competition, or the need to gain additional skills and experience.

Table 10

Distribution of the Respondents' Length of Service with the Present Company

Length of Time	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 months	6	6.78
4-6 months	11	10.17
7-9 months	12	11.86
10-12 months	21	16.95
More than 1 year but less than 2 years	29	23.73
2 years but less than 3 years	20	18.64
3 years and above	10	11.86
Total	109	100%

At the same time, some graduates were able to find jobs more quickly. About 16.95% secured employment within 10–12 months, 11.86% within 7–9 months, 10.17% within 4–6 months, and 6.78% within just 1–3 months. This indicates that while a portion of graduates transitioned smoothly into the workforce, others faced longer delays in matching their qualifications with available opportunities.

Overall, the findings point to varied employment transition patterns—some graduates enter the workforce immediately, while many take a year or more before securing stable jobs. This highlights the importance of strengthening school-to-work transition mechanisms such as internships, job placement services, and stronger industry linkages to help shorten waiting times and improve employability.

The data also suggest that once employed, most graduates can maintain long-term work. This is consistent with Estrellado et al. (2025), who found that a majority of BSOA graduates held regular or permanent positions, with job retention supported by their competencies and strong work ethic. This implies that BSOA graduates of NORSU are equipped with the skills and values needed to sustain stable careers in the industry.

Table 11 presents the job alignment of BSOA graduates. The results show that 23.73% of respondents considered their current job as very relevant to their course, while nearly half (47.46%) said their job is relevant. Meanwhile, 16.95% described their work as neutral (neither related nor unrelated), 8.47% as slightly related, and only 3.39% as unrelated to their degree.

Table 11

Relevance of College Degree to the Present Job of the Respondents

<i>Relevance of Degree</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Very Relevant	24	23.73
Relevant	51	47.46
Neutral	20	16.95
Slightly Relevant	8	8.47
Not Relevant	3	3.39
Total	109	100%

In this study, these categories may be interpreted as follows:

- *Very Relevant* – The job directly applies the knowledge, theories, and technical skills gained from the BSOA curriculum. These roles are often in marketing, sales, advertising, brand management, or logistics, where graduates perform core tasks such as strategy development, customer analysis, product promotion, and market research.
- *Relevant* – The job partially aligns with the field of study. While not fully marketing-focused, it still draws on key business skills like communication, customer relations, and project coordination. This includes jobs in BPOs, government agencies, and finance-related sectors.
- *Neutral*– The job is neither clearly related nor unrelated. These may be support or transitional roles where tasks are more generic, or positions taken out of necessity rather than preference.
- *Slightly Relevant* – The job has minimal connection to the degree. Graduates in these roles may use general soft skills such as communication or customer service, but not in ways that reflect specialized training.
- *Not Relevant* – The job is entirely outside the graduate’s field. This may result from personal circumstances, lack of opportunities, or career shifts, as also noted in Table 6 regarding employment mismatches.

Overall, the findings indicate that a large majority of graduates are employed in positions where they can apply the knowledge and skills learned in their degree program. This is consistent with Albina and Sumagaysay (2020), who also found that graduates often secure jobs related to their course. Such outcomes highlight that the competencies

developed in the BSOA program play a key role in ensuring employability and relevance in the workplace.

Table 12 shows that the largest group of respondents, 49 or 44.07%, have been employed for only 1 to 3 months. This indicates a high proportion of newly hired employees, which may reflect recent recruitment, job changes, or high turnover. The second largest group, 29 respondents (27.12%), have worked for 4 to 8 months, while 26 respondents (23.73%) have stayed for more than one year, suggesting that although many are in the early stages of employment, a notable portion has achieved longer tenure, reflecting job stability. Only 5 respondents (5.08%) reported 9 to 12 months of employment, the least represented category. This may suggest that employees either leave before reaching one year of service or remain beyond it once they pass that stage.

Table 12

Distribution of the Respondents by the Length of Time Before Getting Their First Job After Graduation

<i>Length of Time</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1-3 months	49	44.07
4-8 months	29	27.12
9-12 months	5	5.08
More than 1 year	26	23.73
Total	109	100%

Overall, the findings show that the workforce is composed largely of new employees, with fewer in medium-term employment and a smaller but significant group demonstrating long-term commitment. This trend has implications for employee retention, organizational stability, and the need for effective training and orientation programs.

The data also suggest that many graduates, particularly the 44.07% employed within three months, were able to secure jobs shortly after graduation. This aligns with Isaal's (2021) study, which found that most graduates obtained employment within a short period, showing they possess the skills and work ethic needed for stable jobs. Similarly, Quinto and Posada (2020) reported that 91% of their respondent's secured employment within a year of graduation, reflecting a broader national trend of Filipino graduates entering the workforce soon after completing their studies. This indicates that the employability of BSOA graduates from NORSU is favourable in terms of quick job placement.

Assessment of Employability and Job Preparedness of BSOA Graduates

The third objective of this tracer study is to assess how well the BSOA program has prepared graduates for employment (AY 2005–2023) by examining employers' ratings of job performance, graduates' self-assessment of preparedness, and employer feedback on core competencies such as communication, problem-solving, teamwork, adaptability, and technical skills.

Table 13 shows that most respondents received favourable evaluations from their employers. The largest group, 49 graduates (44.07%), were rated Very Good, followed by 29 (27.12%) rated Good. In addition, 26 graduates (23.73%) earned an Excellent rating, showing that nearly one-fourth of the respondents consistently deliver outstanding performance and are highly valued in the workplace. Only 5 respondents (5.08%) were rated Fair, suggesting a small minority may require improvement. Importantly, no graduate received a Poor rating, meaning none were perceived as underperforming. Overall, this reflects a generally strong workforce quality and good alignment between the graduates' skills and employer expectations.

Graduates' self-assessment also supports this positive outlook. Most reported that their BSOA education adequately prepared them for their current jobs, particularly in administrative and organizational tasks. Employers' feedback confirmed this, with high ratings in key competencies such as communication, teamwork, and adaptability. Technical proficiency and problem-solving were also rated positively, though employers suggested that continued training and exposure to new technologies would further strengthen graduates' performance.

Table 13

Distribution of the Respondents by Employers' Feedback on Job Performance

<i>Employer's Feedback</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Excellent	26	23.73
Very Good	49	44.07
Good	29	27.12
Fair	5	5.08
Poor	0	0
Total	109	100%

Taken together, the results indicate that BSOA graduates from NORSU are well-prepared for employment, demonstrating strong workplace readiness and professional skills. Employers express high satisfaction with their performance and graduates themselves feel confident in applying their academic training on the job. This finding aligns with Layaoen (2024), who reported similarly high ratings for BSBA graduates in areas such as customer service, ethical standards, and interpersonal skills. Overall, the

evidence suggests that the BSOA program equips graduates with competencies that meet industry needs and support long-term career success.

Table 14 shows that most respondents demonstrated a strong sense of job preparedness. A total of 39 graduates (35.59%) were rated Very Good, and 33 (30.51%) were rated Excellent. Together, this makes up 66.1% of the group, indicating that the majority are well-prepared to perform their job responsibilities effectively. Another 26 respondents (23.73%) were rated Good, suggesting they are adequately prepared but still have room to improve. Only a small proportion received lower ratings: 7 graduates (6.78%) were rated Fair, and 4 (3.39%) were rated Poor, showing that a minority may need further training, mentoring, or skills development.

Overall, these findings reflect a generally high level of job preparedness among graduates, with most considered capable and confident in handling workplace tasks. However, the presence of a small group with lower ratings highlights the importance of continuous training and support to help all employees reach higher levels of competence.

Table 14

Distribution of the Respondents' Self-Assessment of Job Preparedness

<i>Job Preparedness</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Excellent	33	30.51
Very Good	39	35.59
Good	26	23.73
Fair	7	6.78
Poor	4	3.39
Total	109	100%

The data also suggest that graduates have a positive perception of their job readiness, with 89.83% rating themselves from Good to Excellent. This aligns with the findings of Pentang et al. (2022), who reported that graduates demonstrate a high degree of competence and professionalism, performing well in both academic and workplace settings. The study emphasized that NORSU's BSOA program not only equips students with technical skills but also strengthens their work ethic and personal qualities, which help them adjust effectively to their professional roles.

In sum, the results indicate that NORSU's BSOA program effectively prepares graduates with the knowledge, skills, and confidence needed to enter and succeed in the workforce.

Table 15 shows that the most frequently recognized strength among employees is adaptability and willingness to learn, cited by 35 respondents (28.81%). This indicates

that employers value flexibility, openness to change, and eagerness to acquire new skills—qualities that are especially important in today’s dynamic work environments.

The next most common strengths were communication skills (23 respondents or 21.19%) and problem-solving abilities (22 respondents or 20.18%). These findings highlight that employers place strong importance on interpersonal competence and critical thinking, both of which are vital for effective teamwork and smooth workplace operations.

Table 15

Employers’ Feedback on the Respondents

<i>Employers’ Feedback</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Excellent communication skills	23	21.19
Strong problem-solving abilities	22	22.88
Adaptability and willingness to learn	35	28.81
Technical skills relevant to the job	10	8.47
Time management and efficiency	11	10.17
Customer service skills	8	8.47
Total	109	100%

Fewer respondents were recognized for time management and efficiency (11 or 10.17%), technical skills (10 or 8.47%), and customer service skills (8 or 8.47%). While these areas remain important, their lower frequency suggests they are either less emphasized by employers or less developed among graduates compared to adaptability, communication, and problem-solving.

Overall, the data suggest that employers prioritize soft skills—especially adaptability, communication, and problem-solving—over purely technical or task-focused abilities. This reflects the growing demand for employability skills and behavioral competencies in sustaining performance and meeting organizational needs.

The relatively lower emphasis on technical and customer service skills points to areas where graduates may further improve. This is consistent with Mainga et al. (2022),

who emphasized the value of soft skills such as communication, learning agility, and problem-solving in graduate employability, while also noting the need to strengthen innovation, creativity, and conflict resolution.

Evaluation of Educational Objectives Attainment of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration Graduates

The fourth objective of this tracer study is to assess how well the BSOA program achieved its educational goals among graduates from A.Y. 2005–2023. Specifically, it evaluates graduates’ ability to: apply office administration concepts in real business contexts, conduct research and analyze data, communicate and collaborate effectively, work independently or in teams, and adapt to new tools, trends, and technologies.

Table 16 shows that the highest-rated competency is the ability to apply office and administrative concepts in actual business situations, with a weighted mean of 3.9 (Very Well), ranked 1st. This reflects graduates’ strong confidence in translating theory into practice—an essential skill for workplace effectiveness.

Table 16

Assessment of the Educational Objectives of the Respondents

<i>Item Statement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. I can apply office and administrative concepts and strategies in real business situations.	3.9	Very Well	1
2. I am skilled in conducting office and administrative research and analyzing data	3.2	Moderately	3
3. I can communicate clearly and work well with others in office and administrative-related tasks.	3.7	Very Well	2
4. I can work both independently and	3.7	Very Well	2

collaboratively on office and administrative projects.			
5. I can adapt to new administrative and office tools, trends, and technologies.	3.7	Very Well	2

The next strongest competencies, all ranked 2nd with a weighted mean of 3.7 (Very Well), are communication and teamwork, the ability to work independently and collaboratively, and adaptability to new tools and technologies. These results demonstrate that graduates possess strong interpersonal and adaptive skills, which are crucial in today's dynamic office settings.

The lowest-rated competency is conducting research and analyzing data, with a weighted mean of 3.2 (Moderately), ranked 3rd. This suggests that while graduates have basic competence in research and analysis, these skills are not as well-developed as their practical and interpersonal abilities.

Overall, the findings indicate that graduates are well-prepared in applying knowledge, communicating, collaborating, and adapting to workplace changes, but they are relatively weaker in research and data analysis. This highlights the need for the program to strengthen training in research and analytics to complement the strong practical and soft skills already demonstrated.

These results are consistent with Domingo et al. (2024), who found that employers of BSBA graduates from NEUST rated communication, adaptability, and teamwork highly but identified research and data analysis as areas needing improvement. Similarly, Johnson (2022) emphasized that while soft skills are in high demand, stronger training in research and technical skills would better equip graduates for industry expectations.

In summary, most educational objectives of the BSOA program were achieved at a high level, but there is a clear opportunity to enhance graduates' research and analytical skills to better align with evolving labor market demands.

Recognition and Contributions of the BSOA Graduates

The fifth objective of this tracer study is to assess whether graduates have received recognition or made contributions to the office administration field. This includes receiving awards or honors related to their work and achieving notable accomplishments in office management, such as leadership roles or motivations.

Table 17 shows that most respondents (79 or 76.27%) reported not receiving recognition from their employers. This indicates that acknowledgment of employees' contributions may be limited, which can affect morale, motivation, and long-term retention, since recognition is closely linked to job satisfaction.

Table 17

Recognition Received by the Respondents

<i>Recognition</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	30	23.73
No	79	76.27
Total	109	100%

Meanwhile, 30 respondents (23.73%) reported receiving recognition. Although this confirms that some graduates are acknowledged, the relatively low proportion suggests that recognition practices are not consistently applied across workplaces.

Overall, the findings suggest that recognition programs or appreciation efforts remain limited. Strengthening recognition—through formal systems or informal acknowledgment—could improve employee motivation, performance, and commitment. The results also imply that while a few graduates have been recognized for their performance, many may still need more time, opportunities for advancement, or supportive work environments that value employee contributions.

This outcome is consistent with Asaari et al. (2024), who found that recognition strongly influences employee motivation ($r = 0.71$) and promotion-related motivation ($r = 0.52$). Likewise, Gopinath et al. (2021) reported that structured recognition and reward systems significantly enhance job satisfaction and performance.

In summary, the lack of widespread recognition among graduates may hinder their professional growth and morale. Encouraging workplaces to adopt clear and consistent recognition practices could help boost motivation and validate the competencies of BSOA graduates.

Table 18 shows that most respondents (80 or 74.58%) reported not receiving recognition from their employers. This suggests that recognition practices are limited in many workplaces, which may negatively affect employees' sense of appreciation, motivation, morale, and overall job satisfaction.

Table 18

Notable Contributions or Achievements of the Respondents

<i>Recognition</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	29	25.42
No	80	74.58
Total	109	100%

In contrast, 29 respondents (25.42%) reported receiving recognition. While this indicates that some employees are acknowledged for their contributions, the percentage remains relatively small compared to those who are not.

Overall, the findings reveal a gap in recognition practices. Since recognition is essential for motivating employees and reinforcing positive work behaviors, management may need to strengthen appreciation efforts—through formal reward programs or informal acknowledgments—to boost performance, engagement, and retention.

The results also imply that while a quarter of the graduates have already made significant contributions in their jobs, most are still in the early stages of their careers or have not yet had the chance to demonstrate their full potential. This aligns with Nguyen and Nguyen (2020), who stressed that early career professionals often need time, organizational support, and mentoring to achieve notable workplace accomplishments.

Identification of Unemployment and Underemployment Factors of BSOA Graduates

The sixth objective of this tracer study is to determine the reasons for unemployment and underemployment among BSOA graduates.

Table 19 shows that the most common reason is the lack of job opportunities in their location (37 respondents or 31.83%), pointing to geographical and regional employment constraints as the main barrier to securing work. The second most cited reason is lack of relevant work experience (30 or 27.27%), highlighting the difficulty many graduates face in meeting employers' expectations despite their educational qualifications.

Table 19

Reasons for Unemployment and Underemployment of the Respondents

<i>Reasons</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Lack of job opportunities in my location	37	31.83

Lack of relevant work experience	30	27.27
Skills do not match available jobs	17	13.64
Pursuing further studies	2	2.27
Family or personal responsibilities	11	11.36
Health-related issues	4	4.55
Low-paying job	2	2.27
Ongoing recruitment process	2	2.27
New graduate with no experience	2	2.27
Just enjoying life first		
Total	109	100%

Other notable factors include skills not matching available jobs (17 or 13.64%) and family or personal responsibilities (11 or 11.36%), both of which limit employability. Less common reasons include pursuing further studies, health issues, low-paying offers, ongoing recruitment processes, being a new graduate, and choosing leisure over immediate employment—each cited by fewer than 5% of respondents.

Overall, the findings suggest that unemployment and underemployment are influenced by both external factors (such as limited job opportunities and skill mismatches) and internal factors (such as lack of experience or personal obligations). Addressing these challenges may require policy interventions—like local job creation and stronger industry-academe linkages—alongside individual efforts such as skills upgrading, internships, and continuous learning.

These results are consistent with Torres (2020), who found that BSBA graduates faced similar barriers, particularly limited employment opportunities, insufficient experience, and skill mismatches. The study underscores the need to enhance practical training, align academic programs with labor market demands, and expand local job opportunities to improve graduate employability.

Conclusions

This tracer study reveals that most NORSU BSOA graduates are young adults aged 22–26, with a strong female majority. They demonstrate high employability, as most secured jobs within one to six months after graduation, mainly in Dumaguete, Bais, and Tanjay. Employment is concentrated in marketing, sales, and logistics, followed by BPO, manufacturing, and government or quasi-government agencies, with most graduates holding rank-and-file positions and fewer in managerial, contractual, or self-employed roles. Graduates reported that their jobs are generally relevant to their course, reflecting strong curriculum alignment with industry needs. They also rated their job preparedness as good to excellent, with employers highlighting adaptability, problem-solving, and communication as key strengths. However, technical and customer service skills were less emphasized, pointing to areas for improvement in training. While most graduates faced no major challenges in job hunting, some cited limited job opportunities and a lack of experience as barriers.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussions, the following recommendations are being proffered:

1. Strengthen Curriculum and Training – Enhance the BSOA curriculum by integrating more technical competencies, customer service skills, and research training, while continuing to develop graduates' adaptability, communication, and problem-solving abilities.
2. Enhance Industry Partnerships – Build stronger linkages with industries and government agencies to expand internship opportunities, industry immersion, and potential employment pathways for graduates.
3. Improve Career Support Services – Provide career development programs such as job fairs, résumé and interview skills workshops, and mentoring to help graduates transition smoothly into the workforce.
4. Establish Alumni and Community Collaboration – Maintain an alumni tracking system and foster partnerships with local government and industries to support job creation and entrepreneurial initiatives, particularly in areas with limited employment opportunities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed ethical standards in educational research. Respondents were informed of the purpose and scope of the study, assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, and notified that their participation was voluntary. The data gathered was used solely for academic purposes and securely stored to prevent unauthorized access.

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